

PSYCHOLOGICAL STATES OF 15-16-YEAR-OLD BASKETBALL PLAYERS DURING PRE-COMPETITION PREPARATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10477391>

Abstract: This article provides information about the psychological conditions of 15-16-year-old athletes before and during the competition, the issues of encouraging them and the processes of preparing for the competition. Also, the development of physical qualities of young basketball players through active games is covered.

Key words: Active games, physical qualities, physical activity, professional skill, methods, sport, competition, physical education, mental preparation.

Introduction:

Fundamental changes are being made in the field of sports development of our country. Taking into account the role of physical education and sports in the healthy education of the future generation, further improvement of sports activities in our country, creation of educational and material-technical base at the level of modern requirements, as well as targeted state-level activities to increase the population's interest in sports is being developed and implemented. Sport plays an important role in understanding the identity of the nation, in its consolidation and unification towards specific goals, and in showing its full potential and power as a nation to the world. From this point of view, the development of the country's sports is an urgent and extremely important issue.

A number of scientific researches devoted to the problems of the theory and practice of the methods of developing the physical qualities of 15-16-year-old basketball players have been carried out. In addition, a number of problems were developed in the scientific works of Z.Azizova, M.A.Gurbanova, M.U.Kasimova, and others, but their work did not adequately cover the qualities of agility, quickness, and strength. Studying the level of development of physical qualities of 15-16-year-old basketball players engaged in the initial training stage:

- ❖ determining the physical fitness of 15-16-year-old students by using movement and relay games, drawing certain conclusions by observing the development process;
- ❖ It consists in determining the effective methods, forms and ways of training physical qualities in students and young athletes, using mobile and relay games in basketball training in general education schools, sports complexes.

Increasing the physical qualities of young basketball players, professional skills, technical-tactical training and interest in the sport of basketball. The results of the study of the experience of dynamic and relay games in the development of physical qualities of young basketball players. It has been proven in the research that the ability to use all the qualities of students in the physical education lesson, using more movement and relay games, in physical education lessons, will be effective in the process of conducting research.

The use of action games in the implementation of 15-16-year-old basketball players through the use of special exercises in training, their activity in the conditions of the formation

of physical qualities, skills and competencies of young basketball players. As a result of regular participation in physical education classes held in secondary schools with basketball, it has a positive effect on vision, hearing, vestibular and other analyzers and shapes their activity.

Exercises used in basketball and this game itself affect the movement apparatus, develop muscle fibers, as a result, their tone increases, physical qualities improve. At the same time, it is difficult to imagine without basketball, the age, gender and other characteristics of children should be taken into account when playing basketball.

"Fight for the ball", "Don't catch the ball", "Hunters and ducks", "Defense the castle", "Kangaroos" to develop the qualities of quickness, agility, agility and dexterity of basketball players; Effective use of games such as "fight for the ball" is appropriate. The constantly changing situation in the game, which requires players to move quickly from one action to another, helps to develop agility. Speed-strength games train strength. In these action games, the players are required to be fast (quick escape, chasing, quick response to sound, visual signal). a constantly changing situation that requires players to move quickly from one action to another helps to develop agility. Fast-paced games train strength. Games that involve the expenditure of more effort and energy than the action performed with great enthusiasm develop endurance. Games help to develop flexibility, which is related to frequent changes of direction. Most of the actions of basketball players are related to the above qualities.

In sports practice, especially in the pre-competition and pre-start situations, there are negative mental states in addition to positive psychological qualities, traits and situations formed as a result of constant training. These negative psychological states or emotions include feelings of excitement and hyper-excitement, anxiety, fear, trembling, convulsions, depression, sadness, and anger. Such feelings, of course, do not leave a negative impact on the quality of training and competition. That is why the priority goal of the psychological preparation process is to eliminate these negative emotions with the help of special exercises, autogenous persuasion, "escape the imagination" and willpower-strengthening formulas, as well as to create a combative state (combat emotions - positive emotional motivation , readiness to load, readiness, determination, restraint) should be focused on "exertion" and polishing.

Psychological preparation is a long-term pedagogical process, in which mental qualities can be formed not only in the process of training and competition, but they need to be improved separately with the help of special methods and tools (exercises). In the practice of training basketball players, it is customary to conduct psychological training in the following two directions:

- *general psychological preparation;*
- *special psychological preparation for a specific competition.*

General psychological preparation. Today's basketball players need coordination, sense of space and time, quick thinking, quick perception and perception of the movements of their teammates and opponents, and other psychological qualities (memory, attention, thinking and h.) requires to be highly formed.

These psychological qualities of a basketball player can be formed during training. For example, as the physical and functional abilities and technical-tactical skills of the participants are formed, as the experience of playing in the training and competitions in the team increases, they have the will, the sense of interval-time, the field of vision, the direction of the

ball. , the qualities of speed, predicting height and height in advance, selecting useful tactics suitable for the situation and countering the opponent's tactics will be refined. If the mechanism and laws of the formation of such psychological characteristics are explained in theoretical and methodological training, and if they are formed in practical training with the help of specially directed exercises (hypotheses, persuasion, goal, probabilities and prediction exercises), the beneficial result will be more significant. does not require proof.

Game tactics and tactical thinking are directly related to the player's psychological capabilities. If the technique (technique of action) is the product of the central (nervous system) and peripheral executive organs of the player's body, tactics (tactics of action, tactical combinations, tactical thinking, prediction, etc.) higher nervous activity — intellectual and is the product of a unit of action. Therefore, it is appropriate to form psychological-physical, psychological-functional, psychological-technical and psychological-tactical training in comprehensive training.

Future competition venues, climatic conditions, and day-night biorhythms will be mastered in simulated conditions. Special psychological preparation for a specific competition. Preparing for a particular competition is a very complex and responsible process.

It is known that every athlete, regardless of his skills and experience, experiences various psychological states (fever-convulsions, apathy - depression, combative state, excitement, etc.) early in competitions and in pre-competition situations. If the game and psychological model (physical, functional, technical-tactical, psychological capabilities) of the future opponent for the player and the team is not well known in detail, negative psychological feelings will increase, even leading to the inability to control oneself. can bring. Therefore, in pre-competition training, all possibilities of the future opponent, including his psychological possibilities, are thoroughly studied. In this case, it is recommended to make extensive use of video films, information provided by "sports intelligence" and other information.

The mental state of the athlete before the competition depends on his success in various previous competitions, and also on the sensitivity of the nervous system to the athlete's state of preparation for the competition. We studied the athlete's preparation for the competition and the state before the competition, divided into the following 4 parts.

1. *Athlete's state of pre-competition preparation.*
2. *Trembling, lifeless state of an athlete in sports.*
3. *Athlete's state of high training and combativeness.*
4. *Athlete's state of mental depression and bad mood.*

The athlete should be given information about his opponent and the conditions of future competitions.

1. To give instructions to the athlete to clearly define the goals and objectives of participating in the competition.

2. To determine the reason, essence and specific purpose of the athlete's participation in the competition, to explain the social significance of winning.

3. To pay attention to the growth of the mental quality of the athlete in planning his activities during the upcoming competition, to improve his tactical and technical mental preparation for the competition.

4. In order to mentally prepare the athlete for the competition, to create unexpected special obstacles, to learn to use additional methods to create skills and abilities that can overcome these obstacles and difficulties.

5. To learn how to use internal mental state management techniques that appear during the competition.

6. Encouraging the athlete to be mentally uplifted at the beginning of the competition, to control the activity of the nervous system, not to be mentally tired, and to achieve more active actions during the competition.

It is necessary for the coach to take into account the emotions and feelings of the athletes when managing their pre-competition condition and influencing their pre-condition training. Coaches and sports clubs are very important for athletes to reach professional level. We can point out 3 main factors in the process of preparing them for competitions. These are: physical training; technical and tactical training; psychological preparation.

Conclusion:

It is worth noting that it is necessary to train athletes not only physically, but also mentally. In addition to the physical, technical and tactical preparation of athletes for competitions, their psychological preparation is important. Not all sports institutions have qualified psychologists. It is desirable to have psychologists working in every sports club, specialized sports institution and sports school to improve the mental preparation of athletes.

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